

FUNCTION OF SYNTACTICAL STYLISTIC DEVICES OF REPETITION

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Abstract: *This article explores the function of syntactical stylistic devices of repetition in literature and rhetoric, highlighting their significance in enhancing meaning, creating emphasis, and evoking emotional responses. Repetition serves multiple purposes, including emphasizing key themes, establishing rhythm and cohesion, and building tension within narratives. It plays a crucial role in character development and can be an effective persuasive tool in speeches and arguments.*

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The device of repetition aims at emphasizing a certain component of the utterance. Being repeated, a language unit obtains additional stylistic information. Consecutive contact repetition is capable of rendering scores of modal meanings and human emotions. Repetition is the most commonly used syntactic-stylistic figure in the language of poetic and journalistic works, a word that expresses meanings such as continuity, is a repetitive form of a word. When thinking about repetition the first thing to consider is the issue of phonetic repetition. Phonetic repetition is reflected in stylistic figures based on inter-line repetition of individual sounds like anaphora, epiphora, alliteration, assonances. The term "sound repetition" was originally coined by O. Brick and was used only for consonant sounds. Later the term was also applied to vowels and consonants in poetic speech. Repetition of vowels, repetition of consonant sound and repetition of syllables are often found in examples of folklore, in poetic speech. Phonetic repetition is mainly characterizes the style of artistic speech [1;23].

By deliberately repeating the phonetic elements the author manages to increase the power of the artistic image and to express his feelings. Sound repetition is especially used to draw the listener's or reader's more attention to the object of the image. The main function of repetition is to make the speech effective, concretize the idea and draw the listener's attention. Linguists I.M. Astafyeva and M.N. Adilov conducted special monographic research on the syntactic and stylistic features of repetition [2;9].

Repetition is a syntactic-stylistic means based on the nature of the oral form of speech which is used to express an emotional state. The use of the repetitive stylistic tool should be natural and the repetition of certain words serves to create a word game in the sentence. For example: For that was it? Ignorant of the long and steally march of passion and of the state to which it had reduced Fleur, ignorant of how Soams had

watched her, ignorant of Fleur's reckless desperation ... ignorant of all this everybody felt aggrieved. (J. Golthworthy) In the small text above, the repetition of the word ignorant is used by the author as a stylistic figure to capture the reader's attention. Reflecting the repetition and its stylistic function Professor A. Mamajonov said that its phonetic, lexical, morphological, syntactic repetitions have such repetition types that are widely used in folklore in the language of fiction. According to the scientist "this situation is a rich material for the analysis of syntactic and stylistic figures as well as an opportunity to conduct separate and important research on repetition to draw appropriate conclusions." Linguist M. Saidova, thinking about the repeated stylistic figure, notes that it has the following types in English. We agree with her about these types of repetitions. 1. A verse is a repetition of an anaphora at the beginning of a passage. Writers use anaphora to create emotional and uplifting forms of speech.

There are also synonymous repetitions that exist in the language. Synonymous repetition adds, expands and details the main content of an idea in the expression of a single meaning. For example: The poetry of earth is never dead, The poetry of earth is ceasing never. (I.Keats) Down with the English anyhow. That's certain clear out you fellows, double quick, I say. You may hate one other, but we hate you most. If I don't make you go, Ahmed will, Karim will, if it's fifty-five hundred years we shall get rid of you. Yes, we shall drive every Englishman into the sea and then" – he rode against him furiously – "and then" – he concluded half kissing him;" you and I shall be friends". There is also a repetition of words consisting of the same stem, which is called half repetition in English. For example: It is my love that keeps mine eyes awake, My own true love that doth my rest defeat, To play the watchman ever for my sake: For the watch I whilst thou dost wake else where, From me far off, with others all to near.(W.Shakespeare) When thinking about synonymous repetition, it is important to think about pleonasm. In pleonasm, not only is the word or tool repeated, but the content is also repeated. It's like an exaggeration but it doesn't add any meaning to the acknowledged idea. Pleonasm is a lack of speech. Pleonasms are synonymous repetitions that are not based on artistic aesthetics. The phenomenon of pleonasm is almost non-existent in the language, especially in Uzbek, but it is transmitted in English. For example: And the books –they stood on the shelf, The wound –it seemed both sore and sad. In both cases, the words pleonasm are replaced by rhymes. The books- they The wound- it The most common type of word-based art is tasdir. The essence of this art is that the word that begins the verse of the poem is repeated at the end of it. In language, speech consists of phonetic units of different sizes. These phonetic units consist of a phrase (sentence), a phonetic word, a word (morpheme), a syllable, and a sound. The above units form a speech chain. A phrase (sentence) is often equivalent to a sentence and the intonational unity between the pauses of speech.

Observations show that the use of repetitive stylistic means in the poetic work of poets plays an important role in ensuring the melody and attractiveness of works. In conclusion repetition especially phonetic repetition gives the work a deep emotional and emotional meaning [3;32].

If one sentence takes the form of a composite sentence, and the second sentence repeats the appearance and construction of the same sentence, then such parallels can be considered complete parallelism: - Overwhelmed, Frederick could open his mouth but could not speak. And Edna could open her mouth but could not speak. Full concurrency always comes with repetition. Sometimes only part of the sentence is repeated, which is partial parallelism. - If she wanted anything somebody was always on the spot to supply it or soothe he without supplying it. If she got into trouble somebody always there to get her out of it. It organizes the rhythm of expression and, thanks to its uniformity, helps to clearly distinguish some parts of the expression. Concurrency is especially common in folk songs and epics: - Work while you work, Play while you play, That's the way To be happy and gay! Repetition is a stylistic tool used to express excitement. Emotional speech is characterized by brevity, logic and repetition of certain parts of the expressed thought. The repetition of certain words and whole phrases in spoken language is certain: she cried out loudly: "Where is my child? But where is my child? I want to know where my child is? In this example, repetition does not fulfill any stylistic function and expresses only a certain mental state of the speaker. Repetition is used as a stylistic tool to attract the attention of the reader. Repetition is divided into the following types in accordance with the structure of other stylistic means: The repetition at the beginning of the verse is called anaphora. For example: - For want of a nail, the shoe was lost, For want of a shoe, the horse was lost, For want of a horse the rider was lost, For want of the rider, the battle was lost [4;91].

Repetitions at the end of a sentence are called epiphora. - When I go into a bank I get rattled. The clerks rattle me. The wickets rattle me, the sight of money rattles me everything rattles me. Duplicate units can appear at the beginning and end of a part, forming a unique circle. This repetition is called ring repetition: - Our hands have met, but not our hearts; Our hands will never meet again. Friends, if we have ever been Friends we cannot now remain: I only know I loved you once, I only know I loved in vain. Our hands have met, but not our hearts; Our hands will never meet again. Another form of repetition is a word that occurs at the end of the first verse and is repeated at the beginning of the second verse: - To Jan it was as though a curtain had been raised in her mind- a curtain from which she recoiled in horror. 5. System repeats are also available: - But two minutes later the sun vanished behind flying cloudy continents, a relative darkness descended on the summer afternoon, and rain too descended-descended in such soaking overwhelming quantities that... 6. There is a type of

repetition called root repetition. Its essence is that in it the word is repeated exactly, but the additional part in one of them is not repeated:

In this method, the same word is not repeated, only the root of the word is repeated, so we come across different words that have different meanings. 7. The next type of repetition is a synonym for repetition. The essence of synonymous repetition is that synonymous means are used to express exactly one concept: - The poetry of earth is never dead, the poetry of earth is ceasing never. There is no need to use objective synonyms here. Concepts can also be brought together as a result of a figurative comparison of events. In this case, the words have a textual meaning. Double synonyms can also give various forms of synonymous repetition. The synonym repeats, expands, details the main content of the idea in the expression of a single, unique meaning. Synonymous repetition in the speaker's speech serves to increase and convince the power of speech, to detail it in artistic speech. While speaking about synonymous repetition, it is necessary to mention the problem of pleonasm. In pleonasm, not only the same word or means is repeated, but also the same content, meaning. This seems an exaggeration; it does not add any value to the recognized opinion.

Ellipsis is an omission of a portion of speech in literary writing. The term ellipsis refers to an incomplete sentence. The ellipse is based on important aspects of speaking. When the speaker is in a state of intense excitement, some parts of the sentence are skipped spontaneously; however, this does not violate the logical connection, which means that any omission in the sentence is not considered a stylistic method. An ellipse is a common form of colloquial speech, but when used in writing it includes new features. An ellipse as a stylistic method adds an extra function to an expression in addition to merging and generalizing. When counting is used as a stylistic tool, the sentence uses things, actions and adjectives. Sometimes these things or actions are similar or close to each other, one in a pair of the other. This method is widely used mainly in the artistic style and serves to express speech. In gradation each specific phrase in a sentence becomes stronger and more effective than its predecessor (in terms of efficiency and logic). Such a definition is subjective because we do not have a linguistic definition to compare it. Synonyms are often used in gradations. The reuse of these synonyms helps to discern the effect. In short, syntactic stylistic devices include inversion, indivisible structures, parallel devices, chiasm, repetition, ellipse, accent, counting, gradation, antithesis, and each of them performs a specific function.

REFERENCES

1. Shakespeare William (1609). Shakespeare's Sonnets: Never Before Imprinted. London: Thomas Thorpe.
2. Bannet Arnold. The Old Wives Tale, 1908. 1171 p.
3. Boboxonova L.T. English Stylistics Tashkent: O.,qituvchi, 1995. –110 p.
4. William W. The French Revolution. –Washington, 1807. –496 p.
5. The Book of Nursery Rhymes 1925. -165 p.
6. Jonathan C. Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary.-Oxford University press, 1995. - pp. 106

